

TECHNOLOGY OF EFFECTIVE USE OF MOVEMENT GAMES IN THE PROCESS OF SCHOOL EDUCATION

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Abstract: Movement games are used as an auxiliary tool in educational and training sessions. Because the game increases interest in students, gives them pleasure, and ensures faster recovery of working capacity. The article presents ideas about the technology of effective use of movement games in the process of school education, types of movement games, goals and objectives.

Keywords: National movement games, methodology, preparation, physical education, lesson, folk pedagogy, technique, physical development.

INTRODUCTION

At the current stage of society's development, raising a well-rounded person is one of the most important and urgent tasks. Our President Sh. Mirziyoyev's Action Strategy for the Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021, paragraph 4.4. presents a number of reasonable ideas regarding the physical development of students. In this regard, the widespread adoption of the Healthy Generation program in our country and the radical reform of the education system are important steps towards the implementation of this ambitious task.

The main goal of the reforms being carried out in the field of education, which is one of the most priority areas of our legal democratic state and open civil society, is a set of measures aimed at improving the quality and efficiency of this process. Therefore, special attention has been paid to the upbringing and health of the younger generation in our country. The promotion of 5 initiatives by our President focuses on meaningful spending of students' free time and providing them with useful activities, and the physical development of young people. Observations and

analysis of experiments show that physical education for primary school students is an important tool in the development of the younger generation. Movement is very necessary for the normal functioning of body parts. The great sage and thinker Abu Ali ibn Sino said: “Physical education is a great way to maintain health,” this idea is reminiscent of the folk pedagogy proverb: “Whoever exercises, his health will be blessed.”

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

The increased attention to physical education can be seen in the organization and regular holding of the “Umid nihollari” sports competitions among secondary school students, or in the fact that Olympic and world champions in many sports have emerged from Uzbekistan, glorifying the greatness of our country to the whole world. In addition, various sports competitions are being organized in all schools and neighborhoods, and some family competitions are also being organized.

Physical education is not a field consisting of purely sports competitions. Through this education, many moral and volitional qualities are formed in children. During the exercises, children develop willpower, speed, agility, endurance, their health is strengthened, their working abilities and mental activity are increased, moral standards such as courage, honesty, determination, independence are formed, and steps are taken towards maturity. Formation through active games is a step forward in the cultural and educational spheres of our society.

The diversity of active games allows them to be used in many areas of the educational process. The purpose of using active games in physical education classes for primary school students is to develop comprehensively mature individuals: hardworking, pure-minded, courageous, steadfast, determined, capable of defending the Motherland in the future. In this regard, the creation of didactic foundations for the use of active games in primary grades of general secondary schools is of great importance within the framework of the theme of updating and enriching the educational content, in particular, the issue of using national active

games, widely interpreted in folk pedagogy in physical education classes, is of great importance today.

Collecting and implementing active games, their rational use is an important task facing us today, both theoretically and practically. This task also places a great responsibility on physical education, which educates the younger generation to be healthy and well-rounded. This problem, which allows educating young people to be physically strong in all respects and aimed at developing the physical qualities of students, requires the consideration of the physical culture of general education teachers in the context of organizational and pedagogical processes, in which we would like to emphasize the great role of active games. Therefore, our goal is to find, develop and implement ways to preserve the national games of our people, which have been passed down from century to century, and to pass them on to the next generation. Active games are one of the most effective methods of physical education and are an important tool for the successful implementation of intellectual, moral and aesthetic education in students. Therefore, it is necessary to pay attention to such aspects of children's games as the spirit, nature, level, and behavior of participants. The same features should be paid attention to when using some of the active games that we recommend to make general and special physical education interesting and useful for 11-12-year-old volleyball players.

Active games are used as an auxiliary tool in training sessions. Because the game increases the interest of the participants, gives them pleasure, and ensures faster recovery of working capacity. Thanks to the game, they forget about fatigue and perform training sessions carefully. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the issue of improving education and upbringing based on the requirements of the Law "On Education" and the "National Program for Personnel Training" has gained importance, and the development of a methodological system of organizational, psychological and pedagogical conditions for the formation of the spiritual, physical and aesthetic culture of students is one of the urgent problems. In this

sense, at the general secondary education stage of the education system, special importance is required to be attached to the upbringing of students as highly spiritual, aesthetic, moral and enlightened, in a word, well-rounded individuals. Aesthetics begins with the labor of humanity and its own activities. This, in turn, stems from its aesthetic attitude to the environment surrounding it and to the being, which is aimed at self-formation, and its own activities. Understanding and feeling the aesthetics of movements as a spiritual force through the use of movement games in one's activities forms the basis for the aesthetic development of the individual. In order for the child's activity to be not difficult and tedious, but to give him aesthetic pleasure, its implementation in the spirit of spiritual upliftment, the accuracy and beauty of movements will save time, inspire the student and attract his attention to this event. In physical education classes for primary school students of general secondary education, planning them (national movement games) is of great importance for the successful organization of the lesson process in the field of aesthetic education of students through movement games. In this sense, at the general secondary education stage of the education system, special attention is required to be paid to the upbringing of primary school students as highly spiritual, aesthetic, moral and enlightened, in short, well-rounded individuals. In this process, it is emphasized that it is important for the younger generation to have knowledge, skills and qualifications appropriate for the development of society. In particular, special attention is required to direct educational and upbringing work towards the formation of the ability to understand the aesthetic foundations of national movement games in primary school students. From this perspective, in the system of important issues that need to be studied in the direction of general secondary education, the problem of developing a pedagogical system for using national movement games in the aesthetic education of students based on modern methods, the content and methodology for introducing new methodological approaches to its implementation in practice should be considered as a priority. Physical education,

taught in the primary grades of general secondary education, DTS, according to its structure and content, proceeds from the priority of the student's personality, his physical development, aspirations, abilities and interests in the process of teaching physical education. However, the tasks presented in the textbooks compiled according to the current programs are not always intended for the aesthetic education of students in the form of action games.

As we said earlier, many action games came from abroad and became nationalized. Because their content, purpose and essence corresponded to the climatic conditions of our country, the social and labor culture of the population. For this reason, it is not surprising that opinions are expressed about the action games of other nationalities that are found in the composition of national action games. Based on the scientific and theoretical considerations of prominent scientists M.Murodov, U.Qambojev, M.Jabborov, J.Toshpulatov, A.Atojev, R.Abdumalikov, T.Usmonkhodjayev, etc., and the content of the games, national action games can be divided into the following categories.

1. Games related to natural landscapes and sciences. Examples of this include games such as “Plant a Seedling”, “Plant Potatoes”, “Rain”, “Santa Claus”. These games serve to develop physical and mental qualities such as alertness, agility, endurance, and so on, based on actions such as weather changes, avoiding cold and rain.

2. Games related to the animal world. Examples of these include “The Birds Flew Over the Water”, “The Hawk Came, My Runaway”, “Wolves and Hunters”, “Wolves in the Wilderness”, “Geese”, “Fox and Rooster”, “Dog and Crow” and many other similar games. In these games, friendship, good and evil, self-preservation, and the development of physical qualities together with the development of physical qualities increase mood. On this basis, children can develop an interest in the animal world and feelings of conservation. 3. Games related to labor. Human activity is determined by mental and physical labor. They

can also be found in the context of movement games. The category of games related to mental labor includes games such as "Counting games", "Writing and guessing numbers", "Singing names or objects in a row and in a mix", "Singing a song while jumping", "Who draws a picture faster", "Arranging shapes and bringing them to their proper position" (making shapes) and similar activities. There are also many movement games reflecting physical labor. These include "Chopping wood", "Shepherding" (shepherd), "Duck driving" (plowing the earth, running), "Hanging", "Pulling", "Lifting", "Riding a donkey", "Foot race", "Train" and others. Their content includes ways of working, methods of performing it, and qualities that express endurance. In general, in all national active games, mental and physical forces are combined, mainly serving to educate physical fitness.

4. Complex and simple active games used at mass cultural events (holidays, weddings, various ceremonies, sports competitions, etc.), and also organized for demonstration and communication purposes. They include elements of wrestling, horse racing, horse racing, racing, throwing stones, tug-of-war, shoulder wrestling, "cockfighting", etc.

5. Games that serve to develop physical qualities are also divided into different categories. The following can be given as examples: speed games: "Trap", "Who is first", "Rabbit without a hole", "Run on all fours" (crawling), "Cracked birds", "The third is too much", various relay races and others; strength games: "White bone", "Chillik", "Many on a horse", "Donkey riding", "Tug of war", "Testing the strength of the wrist", "Pulling on the hands" and others; endurance games: "White poplar, blue poplar", "Get out of the circle", "Olamon race", "Dorboz", "White crow", "Oshiq" (a girl), "Kilichbozlar", "Beshtosh", "Toqqiz tosh", "Orqang kuydi", "Bota soldi", "Tortishmachok", "Koz bag'lash", "Bekinmachok", "Kim keldi", "Zuv-zuv" and others. The above-mentioned complex and simple Uzbek national games directly serve to educate the physical qualities of people of all ages, as well as to form and further improve their human qualities.

CONCLUSION

In developing such qualities as agility, compactness, agility, resourcefulness, and resilience in children, one should not be limited to only movement games in physical education classes. It is advisable to ensure that they freely engage in sports games, gymnastics, athletics, and wrestling in their free time in the yard, street, and playground.

The conclusion is that it is necessary to use movement games, which are divided into various categories, in a timely and purposeful manner.

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